

FEATURES OF THE PROCESS OF FORMING INNOVATIVE STRATEGY UNDER CONDITIONS OF MODERN REALITIES

Yuldasheva Nilufar Abduvakhidovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD) of the Fergana

Polytechnic Institute, Associate Professor of the

Department of Management

e-mail: nilush1986@bk.ru

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The issues of innovative development today are among the most relevant and discussed in the works devoted to the theory of industrial economics. Authors such as A. A. Alekseev [1], M. Porter [2] and others are in solidarity in considering the category of “innovation strategy” as “the core of the long-term development of all processes of economic activity” [3]. Today, in economic science, the main aspects of determining the priorities of the R&D direction, the principles for developing programs of technological innovations are clearly formulated. However, the issues of forming an innovative strategy and factors influencing this process are still not studied deeply enough.

The starting point for the formation of an innovative strategy of an economic entity is the analysis of the state of the external environment, aimed at identifying potential threats and opportunities.

It should be noted that this kind of analysis involves not only monitoring the current business conditions, but also assessing future changes caused, for example, by the development of technological innovations.

After assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the organization, one should begin to evaluate its innovative activity. Under the innovative activity of the organization, we mean the intensity of the activity, characterized primarily by the level of mobilization of the innovative potential of the organization.

The assessment of innovative activity is primarily aimed at ensuring that, when forming the goals of strategic development, within the framework of the innovation strategy, research experience and economic opportunities for introducing innovations are considered, taking into account regional specifics.

The next stage in the development of an innovation strategy is an assessment of the level of innovative potential of an enterprise, which is carried out by evaluating six groups of indicators:

1) personnel: working conditions, humanization of labor, movement of workers, socio-psychological state and labor discipline, personnel costs;

- 2) organizational and technical: the degree of technological equipment, the use of equipment and labor productivity, the organization of production, the quality of logistics, the effectiveness of the management apparatus;
- 3) scientific: information and resource components of the scientific potential;
- 4) marketing: commodity-price and sales policy, marketing resources, level of marketing research;
- 5) environmental: the scale of environmental exploitation activities, the use of resource-saving technologies, the use of treatment facilities;
- 6) financial and investment: solvency and financial stability, cash inflow and outflow, business activity [4].

The assessment of innovative potential in the context of choosing an innovative strategy sets the main goal of identifying the real possibilities of an enterprise for the implementation of an innovative project.

As the final stage in the formation of innovative strategic development alternatives, we highlight the compilation of a SWOT analysis matrix. Identification of the strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise is the basis for assessing the strategic position of the enterprise. The development of an innovative development strategy should be based on the allocation of those internal and external factors that can be considered as the basis of competitive advantages. A comprehensive assessment of the strategic potential of an enterprise makes it possible to assess the current state of the enterprise, the degree and level of innovative activity and the possibility of implementing the planned tasks [5].

In modern economic science, innovative development strategies are conventionally divided into active and passive ones. The choice of the type of innovation strategy should be based on compliance with a number of key criteria.

In particular, organizations that choose an active type of innovation development strategy should be characterized by such features as:

- high rate of renewal of the equipment fleet;
- increase in funding for R&D and innovation;
- positive dynamics in terms of profit and profitability of the enterprise.

The final step in choosing an innovative development strategy is the process of determining the directions and objectives of innovative development and identifying sources of funding for measures to implement them.

The tree of innovative development goals must meet the following requirements:

- completeness (the designated goals should maximally meet all the requirements of stakeholders (owners, customers, suppliers, investors, the state));
- dimension (to assess the effectiveness of the enterprise, clearly defined quantitative expressions are needed);
- priority of goals (gradation of the tree of goals of innovative development in terms of importance, based on the goals of the strategic development of the enterprise);
- the adequacy of the goals set (the enterprise should not set itself obviously unattainable targets, which at the same time should be quite ambitious).

Thus, the choice of an innovative strategy will be carried out taking into account the assessment of both the market needs for innovation and internal factors in the development of the enterprise. In particular, in order to maximize the impact of innovative projects, as well as the fastest transition to a qualitatively new level of development, enterprises need to adjust their development directions, taking into account the phase of development of innovative potential.

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